

Exploring the factors affecting emotion elicitation

Maria Angelica Velazquez* Gül E. Okudan Kremer**

**The Pennsylvania State University, Industrial and Manufacturing Engineering Department
University Park, United States, mav189@psu.edu*

***The Pennsylvania State University, School of Engineering Design, Technology and Professional Programs
University Park, United States, gek3@psu.edu*

Abstract: Often, researchers study human emotions and their effects by way of carrying out experiments that manipulate the emotional states using emotion elicitation techniques. Based on these studies, theories on effects of emotions in human cognitive activities are derived. These theories help designers to understand the effects of emotion in the interaction with artifacts providing insights to incorporate emotion in the design of products. Because of the relevance of the insights, the emotion elicitation methods should be effective and reliable. In this paper, we summarize the factors affecting the elicitation of positive and negative emotions, and propose ways to account them in experimental settings. A conceptual model is presented, along with ideas on how to measure and control such factors. The analysis of these variables and their effects in the valence and arousal of the emotions generated will help designers understand the basis of the emotion elicitation, and will provide insights on the experimental variables in the generation of emotions.

Key words: *Emotion elicitation, positive affect, negative affect, emotion generation*

1. Introduction

Emotion is a mental and physiological state that may be associated with a variety of behavior, mood, temperament and personality. They are reactions to events that are relevant to the goals, needs, and concerns of an individual, encompassing physiological, affective, behavioral, and cognitive components [1].

Emotions are induced and manipulated in experimental settings with the purpose of studying their nature and to understand human behavior in emotional situations. The effects of emotions in cognitive activities such as decision making, learning, generation of evaluative judgments, memory, and behavior have been widely studied by inducing positive and negative emotions in human participants in experimental settings [e.g., 2-7]. Experiments in which emotions have been induced have demonstrated the importance of emotions in human intelligence, rational decision making, social interaction, perception, memory, learning, creativity, attention and reasoning [5-6, 8].

Numerous theories and frameworks have been based on such experiments in an effort to explain the effect of emotions in cognitive activities [2, 9-13]. Such theories help designers understand the nature of emotions, the ways they are generated and their effects in human interaction with artifacts, providing insights to account for

them, and facilitating the incorporation of emotion in the design of products. By eliciting emotions in prospective users, designers may study the influence of their products in the affective state of the user as well as the degree to which their products are robust to overcome pre-existing emotions and promote the desired affects. Due to the relevance of the insights generated from experiments involving emotion elicitation, it is important to have effective and reliable methods for emotion elicitation in experimental settings.

Emotion elicitation consist of the artificial generation of positive or negative affect via the manipulation of environmental factors that directly affect the person in the context where the emotions are to be generated. Emotions may be elicited by using a variety of modalities including exposing the experiment participants to movies, pictures, sounds, facial expressions, behaviors, introspection and storytelling [14].

Although there are multiple techniques for emotion generation, most of these fail to provide details regarding the degree to which emotion valence and arousal levels may vary as a function of specific parameters. For instance, parameters such as exposure time, subject's personality, importance of the goals to be accomplished, degree of exposure to stimulus may be factors associated with differences in the generation of emotion. Most of the existing methods do not provide a detailed and theoretical rationale of why the emotions are being generated. Moreover they fail to explain the type of experimental factors that may affect the degree to which emotions are elicited. We assert that for an elicitation method to be repeatable and reliable, it should provide the means to understand the factors influencing the emotion generation and to account for differences.

Understanding variances in emotion elicitation experiments is crucial for the development of accurate and reliable theories of the effect of emotions in human behavior. The explanations of such differences may explain the discrepancies in observed behavior under induced emotions, and can provide information for specific scenarios, personalities and cases.

Here, we present a conceptual model of the factors affecting the elicitation of emotions in experimental settings, and propose ways to account for the factors that may affect the degree to which emotions are elicited. This model provides insights for the influence of experimental factors on the type and intensity of emotions generated. We introduce the theme of “varying emotion elicitation” as a function of experimental variables. This theme governs the relationships for the estimation of emotional valence and arousal in various circumstances and for multiple populations as explained in our conceptual model. We also outline relevant paths of inquiry for future research while providing insights on effective techniques and strategies to account for emotional states.

2. Review of emotion elicitation techniques

Although there is a wide diversity of strategies to elicit emotions, most of the existing techniques focus on using the visual and auditory domains. As an example, Rostenberg et al. [15] proposed the use of standardized emotional film clips or movies to elicit positive and negative emotions through participant exposure. This method provides a list of films and their emotional categorization. There are limited guidelines on the exposure duration as well as personal variables such as previous exposition and personal preferences. Proposed by Bradley and Lang [16], the International Affective Picture System (IAPS) is a similar method, which is a standardized set of pictures that are proven to elicit specific emotions in the participants. Although the method provides specific

guidelines for its use, it does not provide details on defined relationships between emotional valence and arousal and individual characteristics such as personality and previous experiences. One other method of emotion elicitation by Eich et al. [17], the MCI, consists of placing music (M) and contemplation (C) in an idiographic context [14]. In this technique, the participants are exposed to music to evoke the emotion desired. The participants are not exposed to any experimental conditions until they are sufficiently induced in the desired emotion, which makes the technique more reliable and less prone to variances in the effects of the emotions elicited in the behavior under study.

Other methods like Eckman's Directed Facial Action (DFA) [18] make use of emotional behavior such as facial expressions to generate emotions in participants while others suggest the use of punishments and rewards to elicit emotions [19]. For example, Picard et al [20] proposed the use of a computer game to elicit frustration in the users, combining principles of frustration and reward for goal accomplishment. The game asks the participants to identify the most frequent shape from a group of shapes displayed in a computer screen. Intentional delays in screen transitions are included in the game to generate frustration in the participants. Picard's game also offers a special monetary compensation as a reward the participant with the best time and accuracy scores. Thus, the intentional delays represent obstacles for the goal attainment of winning the special prize. Although this computer game is not a standardized technique for emotion elicitation, it proved to be very effective to elicit frustration in the participants. However, it is limited to elicit frustration and the implementation strategy does not provide means to account for different degrees of emotion elicitation, or for the differences in emotions as various emotions related to frustration may emerge.

In general, these emotion elicitation methods do not provide theoretical explanations of the emotion elicitation. For example, the relationships between the degree of valence and arousal generated and variables such as personality, exposure time and previous experiences are not explained. Most of them assume that an emotion will be elicited, and that the emotion is constant across participants regardless of the personal characteristics of the participants.

Our model of emotion elicitation hypothesizes that the degree of valence and arousal generated depend on a set of individual factors, and thereby provides the means to investigate relationships between individual factors and emotional valence and arousal.

3. Factors influencing emotion elicitation

This section presents the conceptual model with the factors affecting the degree to which emotions are elicited in experimental settings. Figure 1 depicts the conceptual model of the factors and their categories. The factors presented do not constitute a comprehensive list. Rather, they are provided as a preliminary set for variables researchers should consider while studying differences in emotion elicitation across subjects and their relative importance.

Figure 1. Factors affecting the valence and arousal of emotions generated in experimental settings.

3.1. Individual factors

Individual factors such as the personality type, previous experiences related to the type of stimulus presented, individual preferences, tastes, ability to appraise situations, and the set of personal values and concerns may affect the ways emotions are generated. Demographic characteristics such as gender, race, ethnicity, and age may also impact the valence and arousal of emotions generated.

Appraisal theories of emotion state that the emotions are elicited by the evaluation of events and situations [20]. Based on appraisal theories, the human being is composed of a set of pre-determined values for their concerns. Whenever the situation in the world is congruent with the value of the human's concern, a positive emotion is generated towards that situation. The reverse happens when there is incongruence between the world and the human concerns or values for such specific situations, a negative emotion is generated. From the appraisal theories vantage point, it is reasonable to believe that there will be differences in the valence and arousal of emotions elicited as a function of individual values, concerns and appraisal of the situation.

In past studies, researchers used various techniques to eliminate the impact of these individual differences (e.g., counterbalancing participants and controlling the population used). Although such techniques should help to cancel the effects of potential differences, we assert that it is necessary to know the degree to which such variables impact the emotion elicitation, and thus, the observed effects of emotions in behavior under the experimental conditions.

3.2. Experimental factors

Experimental factors such as the length of exposition to elicitation situation, the duration of the stimuli presented, the severity of the interruption for goal attainment, the type of feedback provided unconsciously and consciously by the experimenter, and the explanations given to the participants about the purpose of the study may bias the valence and arousal of the emotion elicited. Although a well-designed experiment should be able to consider and avoid such biases, we believe it is important to understand to which extent such differences in experimental runs may cause different reactions and thus provoke differences in the elicited valence and arousal levels. In general,

the existing methods do not provide details on how to control these experimental factors, or the effects of different levels of these factors in the valence and arousal of the emotions elicited.

3.3. Rewards and punishments

For elicitation techniques in which the emotions are generated by using a reward and punishment system (e.g., Picard's game to elicit frustration), it is particularly important to understand factors such as the degree to which the person is interested in accomplishing the goal and obtaining the reward, and the threat perceived as a consequence of not accomplishing the expected goals. Factors such as the degree of importance of the compensation received upon goal attainment should be considered as well [19].

4. Incorporation of these principles in emotion elicitation

The conceptual model presented in Figure 1 highlights the importance of knowing the effects of external factors in the intensity and type of emotions generated. In other words, experimenters should account for potential impacts of such factors through establishing ways to *control* and *measure* such variables.

A way of controlling may be to limit the sample to a distinct type of population, to expose the participants to a specified time or specified number of stimuli, and to have a standardized procedure for the researcher to execute the elicitation runs. For example, one can execute an experiment in which only persons classified as feelers (F) in the Myers Briggs Test may participate, although this will affect the population for which conclusions are inferred.

Measuring may be an easier way to account for individual and experimental differences and to understand their effects in the emotion elicitation. Instead of controlling the population of participants, we may include the personality type as a co-variate and see if there is any difference in the emotional valence reported by thinkers (T) and by feelers (F). We may also incorporate methods to measure the importance of goal attainment, individual preferences as well as values and previous experiences with the emotion elicitation material. Measuring these variables will allow us to find relationships with the degree of arousal reported. Some of these variables are subjective in nature, and hence, validity and reliability verification in scales and questionnaires should be observed

Numerical measures of these variables enable quantitative analyses of the relationships between the variables and the type of emotions induced as well as the arousal levels reported by the participants. Self-report methods such as the Self-assessment mannequin (SAM), the Affect grid, and the Positive and negative affect schedule (PANAS) provide quantitative measures of the emotions elicited. Numerical measures of emotions will allow the use of statistical methods to discern the relationship between emotional valence and arousal, and the experimental factors that were measured. For example, we may conclude that there is a positive correlation between the participant's age and the level of arousal reported. Other multivariate techniques such as factor analysis may be used to know the most relevant factors affecting the emotion elicitation. After some data manipulation and preparation, statistical analyses and hypothesis testing may be done across emotional valence and arousal levels. Furthermore, mathematical models of the observed relationships can be constructed and used by designers to understand the effects of individual characteristics in the elicitation of emotions.

5. Venues for future research

The relationships presented as part of the conceptual model (Figure 1) are based on the existing theories of emotions such as appraisal theories and reward and punishment theories. Although the proposed conceptual model potentially enhances the awareness on the importance of measuring and controlling variables in emotion elicitation experiments, the proposed effects need to be validated with empirical data. It is necessary to execute experiments to validate the relationships between the variables presented, and the valence and arousal. Empirical testing will also provide detailed descriptions of the relationships and specific effects of the factors mentioned. Empirical tests may be done by designing experiments in which the conditions of the factors may be varied and differences in emotional valence and arousal may be detected. From these experiments mathematical models of emotion elicitation may be created to predict the valence and arousal of emotion as a function of experimental and individual characteristics of the human.

In the paper, we assert the importance of measuring and controlling experimental variables as it is necessary to develop reliable and repeatable methods, and scales to objectively measure subjective parameters such as personality type, preferences, values and previous experiences with the stimulus presented. Our overall goal is to highlight the importance of understanding the basis of emotion elicitation in experimental settings.

Consideration of physical and physiological body responses to emotion

There is vast evidence of the physical expressions of emotion. From facial expressions to the way the subject's make use of instruments while experiencing an emotion. For instance, during Picard's tasks, the frustrated users exhibit a higher number of mouse clicks during frustration episodes. Similarly, the physiological changes in the body have been associated with positive and negative emotions (e.g., heart rate, blood pressure, galvanic skin response).

Physiological measures in particular, may provide continuous data that would allow the detection of patterns and changes in emotion elicitation for a set of experimental parameters. This type of analysis should provide fine-grained information on the changes in emotion elicitation as a function of the variables under study. Physical methods of emotion measurement may also provide information on a continuous basis when the data is collected continuously and analyzed appropriately. Thus, facial expressions, along with physiological responses and overall behavior should be considered as inputs to analyze the effect of experimental factors in the emotion elicitation.

Studying the effect of experimental factors in existing methods

As mentioned in section 2, there are several methods for the elicitation of emotion in experimental settings. Most of these methods do not provide information about the variations in emotional valence and arousal levels as a function of experimental factors. Thus, we assert that there is a void in the published relevant literature, and the effect of experimental factors on the ability of such methods to elicit emotions as well as variations in the degree of emotion elicited should be studied. Mathematical relationships may be generated, and used posterior to data collection to adjust the data and minimize variability.

6. Conclusions

Inherent to the human, emotions serve as motivators for many actions, adding meaning and enriching almost all human experiences. Emotion elicitation in experimental settings allows researchers to study effects of emotions on human cognitive activities and behavior. With this article, we intended to enhance awareness on experimental factors for researchers and designers who use emotion elicitation strategies. As a result of studying the impact of such factors, experimenters can explain why and how emotions are elicited using various techniques, and understand the differences in the valence and arousal of the emotions elicited among participants. Such differences may also explain deviations from expected behaviors or cognitive responses in experiments where emotional states are induced.

Our conceptual model of emotion elicitation suggests that the participants' individual characteristics, experimental variables and the type of reward and punishment are aspects of emotion elicitation with potential effects on the valence and the degree of arousal elicited. Thus, it is necessary to find effective and reliable methods to measure these factors and to control the emotion elicitation experiments.

7. References

- [1] Brave, S. and C. Nass (2003). Emotion in Human-Computer Interaction. In J. Jacko and S.A. (Eds.). *The human-computer interaction handbook: fundamentals, evolving technologies and emerging applications*. L. Erlbaum Associates Inc.
- [2] Simon, H. A. (1967). "Motivational and emotional controls of cognition." *Psychological review* 74(1): 29-39.
- [3] Damasio, A. R. (1994). *Descartes' error : emotion, reason, and the human brain*. New York Avon Books.
- [4] LeDoux, J. E. (1997). *The Emotional Brain: The Mysterious Underpinnings of Emotional Life*. New York Simon & Schuster.
- [5] Eich, E., J. F. Kihlstrom, et al. (2000). *Cognition and Emotion*. New York Oxford University Press, USA.
- [6] Picard, R. (1997). *Affective Computing*. Cambridge, Massachusetts The MIT Press.
- [7] Mahlke, S. (2007). Aesthetic and Symbolic Qualities as Antecedents of Overall Judgements of Interactive Products. *People and Computers XX — Engage Proceedings of HCI 2006* N. Bryan-Kinns, A. Blanford, P. Curzon and L. Nigay. London, Springer 2: 57-64.
- [8] Forgas, J. (2001). *The Affect Infucion Model (AIM): An Integrative Theory of Mood Effects on Cognition and Judgment Theories of Mood and Cognition: A User's Guidebook* L. L. Martin and G. L. Clore. New Jersey Lawrence Erlbaum Associates

- [9] Clore, G. C. and K. Gasper (2000). Feeling is believing: Some affective influences on belief. *Emotions and Beliefs: How Feelings Influence Thoughts* N. H. Frijda, A. S. R. Manstead and S. Bem. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press: 10-44.
- [10] Bower, G. H. and J. P. Forgas (2000). Chapter 3: Affect, memory, and social cognition *Cognition and emotion* E. Eich, J. F. Kihlstrom, G. H. Bower, J. P. Forgas and P. M. Niedenthal. New York Oxford University Press.
- [11] Clore, G. L., R. S. Wyer, et al. (2001). Affective Feelings as Feedback: Some Cognitive Consequences *Theories of Mood and Cognition: A User's Guidebook* L. L. Martin and G. L. Clore. New Jersey Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- [12] Isen, A. M. (1978). "Affect, accessibility of material in memory, and behavior: A cognitive loop." *Journal of personality and social psychology* 36(1): 1.
- [13] Schwarz, N. and G. L. Clore (1988). How Do I Feel About It? The Informative Function of Affective States. *Affect, Cognition and Social Behaviors*. K. Fiedler and J. Forgas. Lewistown, NJ, Hogrefe, Inc.: 44-62.
- [14] Gray, E. K. and D. Watson (2007). Assessing positive and negative affect via self-report. *Handbook or emotion elicitation and assessment*. J. A. Coan and J. J. B. Allen. London Cambridge University Press.
- [15] Rostenberg, J., Ray, R. D., and Gross, J. J., (2007). Emotion elicitation using films. *Handbook or emotion elicitation and assessment*. J. A. Coan and J. J. B. Allen. London Cambridge University Press.
- [16] Bradley, M. M. and Lang, P. J., (2007). The international affective picture system (IAPS) in the study of emotion and attention. *Handbook or emotion elicitation and assessment*. J. A. Coan and J. J. B. Allen. London Cambridge University Press.
- [17] Eihc, E., et al. (2007). Combining music with thought to change mood. *Handbook or emotion elicitation and assessment*. J. A. Coan and J. J. B. Allen. London Cambridge University Press.
- [18] Eckman, P. (2007). The directed facial action task: Emotional responses without appraisal (2007). *Handbook or emotion elicitation and assessment*. J. A. Coan and J. J. B. Allen. London Cambridge University Press.
- [19] Rolls, E.T., (2007). Emotions elicited by primary reinforcers and following stimulus-reinforcement association learning. *Handbook or emotion elicitation and assessment*. J. A. Coan and J. J. B. Allen. London Cambridge University Press.
- [20] Roseman, I. J. and C. A. Smith (2001). Appraisal processes in emotion. K. R. Scherer, A. Schorr and T. Johnstone. New York Oxford University Press.